

IMPORTANCE OF ETHICS AND BEHAVIORAL CULTURE IN CIVIL SOCIETY

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Abstract. *This article is written about the importance of moral and behavioral culture in civil society. It is acceptable to show the place of culture in civil society and the importance of protecting people's moral standards. This article tells the readers about the importance of humanism, respect and appreciation of literature in civil society. Explains the importance of protecting human rights, fairness and respect for all people in general society. This topic is important in interpersonal relations and mutual appeals of society. These truths and concepts improve communication between people and society and improve effective communication.*

Keywords: *justice, respect, creativity, love, self-awareness, contentment, loyalty, honesty, freedom.*

It is necessary to take into account the importance and place of the culture of ethics and behavior in civil society, because moral spirituality is the main complex importance of human nature, which includes social ethics and our life tasks. Ethics and behavior are important in civil society, and they directly affect the reward and appeal relationships between people. Ethics and behavior are key indicators of reducing chaos between people and learning self-awareness and respect for humanity. One of the important issues is the priority of the culture of ethics and law, as well as the culture of behavior, which has a special place in civil society. Morality is one of the main types of social norms and reflects the internal mental attitude of a person to social and legal events in terms of good and bad, duty and conscience. Moral norms or ethical norms refer to the form of moral requirements that regulate the behavior of people through general orders and prohibitions imposed on the same actions. This essence is a progressive essence that should be implemented with great success in all civil societies. The culture of ethics and behavior in civil society is changing, people are engaged in other rights of civil society. Civil societies should help unite people's living spaces in moral and behavioral cooperation, create guidelines for the protection of all citizens, prevent moral and physical harm, and cooperate in legal claims, citizenship and rights. They are impressive and demanding displays of skill.

Another peculiarity of legal norms is that what is possible and what is not possible is strictly, clearly indicated in the law and other regulatory documents. In this regard, it should be noted that legal norms, unlike some social norms, for example, moral norms, are related to written speech and textual studies. Legal norms regulating personal behavior are prepared in the form of specific documents that have the force of law.

Fichte explains the difference between ethics and law according to his philosophical system. The right should be limited to the sphere of the perceptible world and should not apply to the inner "I" of a person, that is, it should not interfere with the way of thinking and mental state of a person. After all, these are beyond the scope of moral legal relations. Legal law, unlike moral law, does not require good will from a person, it applies to external actions.

Manners, morals, reputation, ethics of humanity in all eras, moral relations between people have been regulated on the basis of political, legal, and economic criteria. Especially in the eastern nations, in particular, morality and ethics form the basis of human relations of our people: in the field of political, legal, economic relations, moral criteria prevail.

Behavioral culture is a collection of patterns of behavior in a person's daily life. It reflects the expression of moral, ethical and aesthetic standards inherent in this behavior. That is, behavioral culture is a set of socially important qualities formed in a person, his daily behavior based on the norms of spirituality, moral and aesthetic culture in society. If spiritual and moral standards determine the content of people's behavior and warn them about how to act in certain situations, then aesthetic standards show how a person should fulfill moral requirements in his actions, these standards are his lifestyle which shows how it naturally fits with a person's personality. Determines what will become the rules of everyday life. For example, if the requirement to respect people is applied to behavior in everyday life, it is manifested in politeness, gentleness, vigilance, not wasting other people's time. The demand for loyalty to one's obligations is manifested in the culture of dealing with the correct fulfillment of promises, the timely and efficient performance of agreed tasks, and the return of deposits. According to the form of its manifestation, honesty is expressed in correctness, justice, not betraying the truth. Human behavior is studied by such sciences as ethology, psychology, sociology.

In order to clarify the nature of this phenomenon, its primary definition is as "a phenomenon characteristic of all living beings, necessary for their interaction with the environment, triggering and directing movement activity". It is appropriate to use it. In addition to being a natural activity, as a result of the interaction of natural and social environmental factors, it is essentially a phenomenon directed to social needs within the norms and rules of people's coexistence.

At today's completely new stage of the socio-political and economic life of our country, human well-being, human rights and dignity are set as the highest goals. This means the formation of a completely new spiritual space, a society based on enlightenment. In this respect, "spiritual space" and civil society develop in an interdependent and dialectical relationship. According to President Sh. Mirziyoyev, the answer to the question 'what is the new spiritual space?' is "In my opinion, this is an enlightened society that clearly reflects the spiritual image of New Uzbekistan that we dreamed of, that our people aspire to, and that our country lives in prosperity".

Behavior is one of the concepts of ethics. This is a moral phenomenon related to the character of a person, and it is understood that the character of a person is manifested within the framework of morality. A person's actions within the framework of ethics include manners and ethics in addition to behavior. If manners consist of actions that leave a pleasant impression on a person, but are not important enough to change the family, society, community and human life, then morality is a set of different actions that can affect something. Morality is manifested in socialized concepts and principles such as good and bad, justice, humanity, selflessness, manners in concepts such as good and bad, duty, generosity, hospitality, and manners in modesty, honesty, truthfulness is manifested in such concepts as honesty, integrity.

In Eastern philosophy and ethics, these three moral phenomena are considered differently, although they are not strictly limited.

This article describes the importance of morals and behavior culture in civil society, that a person should always be polite and respectful. It describes how this culture is reflected in every

citizen and society, how important human considerations are in the implementation of laws and regulations and in the development of human relations.

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